

Blueprint of EOSC-ENTRUST to enhance European interoperability

Secure processing of health data: EOSC and European Health Data
Space approaches and synergies
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Pål Sætrum

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 eOSC | **ENTRUST**
European Network of Trusted Research Environments

ENTRUST: Creating a European network of trusted research environments

Fundamental challenge: research and policy-driven analyses on sensitive datasets

Q: *“Health issues in relation to income, education, age, and area of residence?”*

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Common user journey:

1. Discover data / plan research
2. Get access to data
3. Analyze data
4. Report / publish results

Architecture for interoperable sensitive data research

1. Discover data / plan research (R)
2. Get access to data
 - a. Register / apply (R)
 - b. Join data (IG)
 - c. Make available (IG)
3. Analyze data
 - a. Local (R)
 - b. Remote (R)
4. Report / publish results (R / IG)

R: Researcher

IG: Information Governance

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European Network of Trusted Research Environments

DARE UK Federated Architecture Blueprint (zenodo.org/records/14192786)

The Blueprint – Year 1

- Focus: Interoperability
 - Requirements – from Drivers (research domains)
 - Capabilities – from Providers (existing TREs)
 - What is needed to form a federation of TRE providers?
- Caveats:
 - No assumptions or requirements regarding TRE implementations
 - No minimum TRE requirements specified
 - Possible: Specific SATRE levels, ISO27001, ...
 - ...but a federation should agree on some minimum standard

The ENTRUST Architecture Blueprint

Supporting federation level requirements: ENTRUST Federation Services

- Coordinating functions defining the federation
 - Participants
 - Users
 - Projects
 - Datasets
- User training
- User certification
- Monitoring/Compliance

ENTRUST Trusted Research Environments

- Defined capabilities
 - Research Analytics Zone (SPE)
 - Secure Data Zone
 - Query Management Zone
- TRE-specific user training
- Actors with defined roles
 - Researcher
 - Data Controller
 - TRE Governance

ENTRUST Research Analytics Zone TRE

- PI instead of TRE act as information governance
- Current practice for mapped Drivers

ENTRUST Secure Data Archive

- Specialized SDZ
- Contains defined datasets
- Supports
 - Data publishing
 - Data access requests

Moving forward

- Internal input
 - Gap analyses
 - Refined user journeys
 - Refined requirements
- External developments
- The Blueprint – Year 2
 - Operating procedures
 - Interface definitions

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Research Environments

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